

TEACHER SKILLS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING PHRASEOLOGY

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Annotation: The purpose of this scientific article is to show the important aspects that should be focused on the teaching of phraseology and to show that it depends on the teacher's skill in using various interesting approaches in the process of teaching.

Key words- teaching phraseology, phrase, idiom, L2 learners, linguistic systems, context-based strategy, teacher's role.

Introduction

The teaching of vocabulary has become essential in foreign language teaching and learning, particularly in the latest years. Phraseology is one of the key components of language due to its high and spontaneous occurrence in daily conversation. The complete lexicon of English is enormous. According to Hill (2001:48), "the mental lexicon on any individual is huge; consisting as it does of a vast repertoire of learned phrases o varying degrees of fixedness". Such phraseological units are usually considered quite difficult for learners owing to two main reasons: their cultural backgrounds and their conventionality, normally significantly different from the learners' mother tongue. However, it is undeniable they are primary to achieve a good command of the language, and ultimately, a proper communicative competence. Undoubtedly, we can state that language is not something isolated, but a social and cultural tool; therefore, the phraseological competence of a speaker depends to a great extent on the cultural knowledge of the linguistic system he/she is involved in. Hence, the situational context really matters

while learning and it is the one that asks for specific utterances and expressions that fit particular situations. These special features of languages and people should be explained and analyzed by L2 learners so that they are able to think differently and immerse themselves into the foreign language's environment.

Methodology

As phraseology constitutes an immense field, teachers struggle to determine which phraseological units are adequate to each level they are in charge of. Obviously, the teacher's role becomes more complicated and involves a greater effort when deciding to include phraseological content in their everyday teaching, since they should also cope with historical, social and ethnographic teaching, but this proposal is said to ensure success. Though there is a wide range of investigations based on the techniques of teaching English phraseological unit with expressing meaning, such as context-based strategy, teaching idioms with using theme, through dialogue writing, guessing game, TV commercials and role play activities.

Data collection and analysis

Teach phraseological units in spoken form, not written, and explain to students how they are conversational, rather than formal. Have students practice the phraseological units in dialogue to help them understand they're used in spoken colloquial English. Don't just hand out a long list of phraseological units. Be sure to provide a small selection of 5–10 phraseological units (or less!) and explain each one. By using idioms, set expressions, the learners' speaking skills are increased. The original contribution of our study is developing the approach to improve speaking skills through phraseological units as well as increasing motivation of students. And now let's look through some teaching technique which we have mentioned above. Use a theme. A great way to teach phraseological units is to use a theme. Most idioms in English fall into a thematic group. For example, you could use all weather-related idioms or teach context-related. By using a common theme

to teach idioms, it's easier for students to grasp the meanings of the phrases, and see how similar words can mean very different things. Teach phraseological units with pictures. Provide a picture to explain the context. This works best if you show an image that humorously illustrates the literal meaning of the phraseological units. It will make students laugh, but also help them understand or guess what a phrase means. Idioms are full of colorful imagery, perfect for a flashcard or photo. Show the picture to your students and have them guess the meaning of the phraseological units. For example: Money talks (show the picture related to this set expression) Meaning: (used to say that money has a strong influence on people's actions and decisions) Dialogue Writing and Role-play in Reading. Dialogues can provide situations for students to practice ordinary conversation and offer students ample practice with basic speaking skills in context. Firstly, dialogues can be viewed as short plays and used for students to act out rather than simply read aloud. Moreover, the dialogues the students write function as basic communication at all levels. In addition, putting pupils into pairs for the role-play in the daily dialogues is an effective way of oral practice for various ages and levels. Moreover, students learn better when they are provided with collaborative activities because they can interact with peers and share fun in learning. For instance: A pretty penny. Meaning: people who is happy and have much money.

Result and discussion

Guessing game. Write three or four idioms on the board that all touch on one theme (e.g. money, body parts). Have students work in groups to see if they can guess the meaning of the phraseological units. Walk around your classroom and check their answers awarding points for any correct definition. Then share the meanings of the phraseological units with your class and give them an example in context. Move on to another group of idioms around a second theme. Repeat the activity. The first team to reach ten points wins the game. One of the basics for teaching is to conduct lessons that interest your students. Bored students won't

remember much of the lesson. Refrain from giving long lectures that will only encourage your students to wander slumber land. Instead, keep students involved and interacting with them in English. Some students may prefer to listen quietly as they are shy to make any comments. If this kind of interaction makes your students nervous, provide plenty of support by giving clear and very specific directions. In addition, make your lessons livelier by adding games or using real-life objects such as a telephone, cook book, or money box. You can also bring your students out of the classroom for an educational tour. This will greatly increase their attention lifespan and assist to absorb the knowledge easily. Another effective way to attract their attention for learning phraseological units is to provide some rewards during the lessons. Studies have shown that students will be able to learn better when they perceive a personal reward. To boost internal motivation, remind them of the benefits that English can provide, such as English-speaking friends, better job opportunities, easier making money, or less stress at the doctor's office, and then teach language that will bring them closer to those benefits. External motivation can be achieved by praise and encouragement as well as tangible rewards like prizes or certificates. These rewards have been proven to be very effective in encouraging the students to put in extra efforts in their daily learning. Learners will remember material better and take more interest in it if it has applicable contextual meaning.

Conclusion

This means that good teachers should be able to relate the teaching materials to daily usage or practical examples. By providing appropriate applications, students will be able to remember them better and longer. With supporting ideas which is mentioned above studying idioms via TV commercials teaching technique proves to be very fruitful. This teaching technique is often funny to watch but they represent a huge language work-out, too. “At an advanced level, culture becomes an even more important part of the syllabus, and media are the great way to present

culture”. On the other hand, TV commercials are culturally distinctive, so are the idioms.

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